

Peculiarities of the Legal Regulation of Labor Depending on the Nature of the Employee's Labor Relationship with the Employer and the Place of His/Her Work

Orazliyeva Rushana

Law school of Navoi region

Abstract: This article describes the principles of the legal procedure of working on a substitute basis. Also, some aspects of working on a substitute basis are explained.

Key points: External accommodation, internal accommodation, working time, vacation, salary, accommodation, specific features of accommodation.

Peculiarities of legal regulation of labor of persons working on the basis of employment A certain part of the population of our country who are able to work prefers to work on a temporary basis in addition to the main job. This situation is referred to as temporary work in the labor legislation. Chapter 26 of the Labor Code, "Section 1. Peculiarities of the legal regulation of the work of persons working on a temporary basis", articles 432-442, provide the legal basis for working on a temporary basis. In this legal source, the concept of work on the basis of residence, restrictions on work on the basis of residence, documents to be submitted when hiring on the basis of residence, employment contract on work on the basis of residence, work on the basis of residence on the basis of the employee's work book. Norms such as entering information on, length of working time during work on the basis of the seat and its accounting are mentioned.

Part-time work means that an employee, in addition to performing his main job, performs other paid work based on an employment contract in his free time from his main job

Work on the basis of substitution is divided into two types: internal substitution and external substitution.

Internal substitution is the performance of work on the basis of substitution by an employee at his main place of work.

External substitutability is the performance of work on the basis of substitutability by an employee at another employer.

Persons entering employment on a temporary basis are asked to submit several documents.

Persons who are employed on the basis of foreign employment must submit the following documents:

- a passport or a document that replaces it or an identification ID card;
- a certificate from the main workplace in the form approved by the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- recruitment on the basis of employment, which can only be done by persons with a certain length of service in accordance with the law
- a certificate from the main workplace in the form approved by the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- recruitment on the basis of employment, which can only be done by persons with a certain length of service in accordance with the law a certified copy of the labor record at the main place of work or an extract from the electronic labor record;
- a diploma, certificate or other document about education or professional training, if such work requires special knowledge or special training;
- a certificate on the nature and conditions of work received from the main place of employment during employment with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions;
- a pension book with savings.

The employer does not have the right to require the employee to submit any documents when hiring on the basis of internal placement.

An employment contract will also be concluded with the employees who are employed on the basis of the position. This employment contract must state that the work is performed on a temporary basis. In the labor contract concluded with the employees working on a temporary basis, the place of work, work duties, starting date, terms of payment for labor, working hours and rest periods are indicated. According to Article 438 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan remuneration for the work of persons working on a temporary basis is carried out in proportion to the time worked, according to the production result or other conditions specified in the labor contract.

In accordance with the labor contract, the remuneration for the work of substitutes:

- a) in the form of payment for labor - for work actually performed;
- b) payment of labor wages is carried out in a time-wise manner - in proportion to the time worked.

In districts where district coefficients and salary increments have been set, the payment of wages to persons working on a temporary basis is carried out taking into account the coefficients and increments. - will be calculated separately.

Persons working on the basis of substitutes also take additional vacations. should be on time.

The employment contract concluded with a person who works on the basis of a substitute, provided by the law, also includes:

This job can be terminated when an employee, who is the main place of work for him, is accepted, and in the event that work on a substitute basis may harm the health of the employee, other persons, or the safety of the production process.

If the employment contract concluded with the employee is terminated due to the above circumstances, the employee will be paid severance pay in the amount of two weeks' average salary.

For example: a teacher invited from a school on the basis of substitution is paid hourly for the time worked. raised In accordance with the regulation, hourly payment for the work of pedagogical staff is replaced by teachers and other specialists recruited from other institutions, as well as teachers and specialists recruited from other schools for the pedagogical work. is used by the heads of general education institutions to pay for the training hours.

In conclusion, it should be said that a substitute is an employee who works in spare time from the main working hours under the employment contract and receives wages in proportion to the time worked - in the form of overtime wages for the work actually performed.

List of used literature and websites:

1. Labor Code
2. Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the procedure for working on the basis of tenure and in several professions and positions"
3. www.lex.uz